

Contract no. 266505

EUPHRESCO ERA-NET

European Phytosanitary (Statutory Plant Health) Research
Coordination II: Deepened and enlarged cooperation between
phytosanitary research programmes

Coordination and Support Action

6-Month Project Report

Report Period Covered: 1st January 2011 – 30th June 2011
Date of Report Preparation: 31st July 2011
Start Date of Project: 1st January 2011
End Date and Duration: 31st March 2014 (39 months duration)

Project Coordinator: Dr Alan Inman
The Food and Environment Research Agency
Tel: ++44 (0) 1904 465641
Email: alan.inman@fera.gsi.gov.uk

Project Manager: Dr Elspeth Steel
The Food and Environment Research Agency
Tel: ++44 (0) 1904 462323
Email: elspeth.steel@fera.gsi.gov.uk

SECTION 1: SUMMARY OF MAJOR PROGRESS AND MILESTONE COMPLETION DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD

- WP1: The project started on 1st January 2011; all contracts have been signed and the first payment has been received.
- WP1: The first project meeting (kick-off meeting) was held on 24rd-25th March 2011 in Copenhagen. The first Project Management Group (PMG) meeting was held on 24th-25th February 2011, and the 2nd PMG Meeting was held on 23rd March (the day before the kick-off meeting).
- WP1: The Project website has been re-launched (www.euphresco.org).
- WP2: the network is being implemented. Some discussions about EPPO and/or DG SANCO providing some support for the long-term EUPHRESCO network have taken place.
- WP3: The WP leader (AT-AGES) and partners have developed a long list of topics for the 1st round of transnational research calls/projects. The long list has been rationalised. For each topic being taken forward, a Topic Coordinator has been assigned and draft Topic Description produced. The work is on track.
- WP4: most EUPHRESCO partners have enlisted to collaborate in one or more of the task groups that will produce the deliverables. This demonstrates commitment and interest.
- WP4: An internal workshop is being organised to coincide with the second PMG meeting being held in Paris at the EPPO HQ at the end of September 2011. It will primarily discuss issues relating to the use of the website as a platform.
- WP5: the workshop for new partners was held alongside the kick-off meeting. New partners have chosen mentors from the old EUPHRESCO-1 partners.
- A summary of progress for milestones scheduled for completion within the period (months 1–6) is given below:

Milestones in Period	Milestone Short Title	Target Date	MS Status
MS 01 WP1	Consortium agreement finalised and signed	Month 3	In progress
MS 02 WP1	Governing board and project advisory group membership developed	Month 3	In progress
MS 03 WP1	EUPHRESCO website updated	Month 3	Completed
MS 04 WP1	Kick-off meeting held	Month 3	Completed
MS 10 WP2	NMG and portfolios set up	Month 1	In progress
MS 15 WP3	Funding consortia for 1 st round of topics	Month 7	Completed
MS 37 WP5	kick-off workshop for new partners/observers	Month 3	Completed

Key to milestone progress/status:

- Completed
 In progress (no significant impact from delay expected)
 Not started (and/or impact from delay expected)

SECTION 2: TECHNICAL PROGRESS DURING THE PERIOD (WPS 2, 3, 4, 5)

WP2: Implementing, testing and refining the long-term self-sustainable network structure

Aim:

WP2 aims to implement, test and refine the proposed model network structure and *modus operandi* from the current EUPHRESKO project. The overall aim is to ensure that the EUPHRESKO network can continue in a durable and self-sustainable way after 2013, in order to deliver effective transnational research coordination and collaboration in support of the Community Plant Health Regime. Further, it aims to build confidence and experience in the network's management structures, *modus operandi*, processes and tools that are needed to implement transnational research, thereby demonstrating the added value and benefits of involvement in the network. The work will consolidate and build on the success of previous EUPHRESKO-1's outputs and establish a culture of collaboration and a regular network routine.

The main objectives are:

- To implement and establish the proposed (from EUPHRESKO-1) structure and *modus operandi* of the long-term self-sustainable network.
- To evaluate and refine the structure and *modus operandi* of the long-term network of funders to ensure that a strong, long-lasting and self-sustainable network emerges.
- To maintain ongoing core network activities that underpin transnational research coordination and collaboration, e.g. mapping activities and database updating; dissemination of transnational research outputs; advising on plant health research priorities in FP7; maintaining linkages to key stakeholders; maintaining the EUPHRESKO toolbox.

Summary of WP2 progress for milestones/deliverables since the project's start:

WP2 Milestones		Target	MS Status
MS10	NMG and portfolios set up	Month 1	In progress

WP2 Deliverables		Target	DL Status
D2.1	NMG portfolios	Month 3	In progress

Key to milestone progress/status:

- Not started (and/or impact from delay expected)

Sub-WP 2.1. Implement the long-term network leadership & management structure

- The 'starting' Network Management Group has been established. It comprises the previous EUPHRESKO-1 workpackage leaders (AT-AGES; DE-JKI; FR-DGAL; NL-EL&I; UK-Defra) for continuity, though membership may change, i.e. testing a model that involves rotation of membership. NMG Portfolios of responsibilities were outlined in the proposal and individual members of the NMG assigned to lead them.
- Assignment of other partners to help with delivery groups was discussed what the kick-off meeting. The portfolios have been partitioned into more concrete tasks for which partners' contribution is asked. An internal timetable for these tasks is currently under development. Membership and terms of reference for these portfolios and delivery groups is still being finalised.
- In summary, the implementation of the network has begun and is functioning, but some refinement of portfolios and their delivery groups is on-going.
- In terms of the longer-term network's sustainability and support, EUPHRESKO has been involved in two activities, responding to requests by external bodies:
 - As part of the Review of the EU Plant Health regime, DG SANCO asked EUPHRESKO to outline (with costings) ways in which DG SANCO might support EUPHRESKO activities in the long-term, if resources were available as part of the new regime.
 - One EPPO member (Austria) proposed that the EPPO Executive Council discuss, in its meeting in September 2011, whether the coordination of European research might fit within EPPO's portfolio and whether the EPPO Secretariat could provide the structures for the long-term sustainable EUPHRESKO network. In response to the resulting request by EPPO on resource implications, EUPHRESKO provided the information on expected costs for specific network activities that would require resourcing in the long-term network (i.e. maintaining the website and providing a network secretariat). This Austrian suggestion regarding EUPHRESKO sitting under EPPO was also discussed in the COPHS meeting on 7-8 June 2011.

Sub-WP 2.2. Maintain on-going network activities

Routine on-going activities fall to individual NMG portfolios. Activities in the period include:

- Advising on FP7 Plant Health research priorities: this is done under a mandate from the COPHS (EU Council Working Party of Chief Officers of Plant Health Services). Two topics were put forward and one of these, with the support also of DG SANCO, has been included in the 2012 Workprogramme call. Contact with the new officer in DG Research (Juli Mylona, replacing Jean-Francois Maljean for Plant Health FP7 issues) has been made and is ongoing.
- Implementation of transnational projects: this is ongoing – see WP3.
- Mapping activities: the PMG agreed that the timetable for mapping national programmes in WP2 should be aligned with that in WP5.

- *Linkages (European)*: EUPHRESCO is now formally linked to other KBBE ERA-Nets through its participation in PLATFORM. EUPHRESCO attended and presented at the 'Continuing ERA-Nets' workshop organized by the Commission in November 2010.
http://netwatch.jrc.ec.europa.eu/nw/index.cfm/static/event_5.html
- *Linkages (international)*: In the period, we have made contact with some potential non-European collaborators in Canada, who are part of a the larger QUAD that includes USA, NZ and Australia, and linked to the International Forestry Quarantine Research Group (<http://www.forestry-quarantine.org/>) which has an association with the IPPC. The IFQRG has an aim to "Identify and undertake collaborative scientific research aimed at high priority forestry quarantine questions". This links to WP5 activities on more international and sector-based enlargement of EUPHRESCO activities. In the newly commissioned EUPHRESCO Project on *Anoplophora* longhorn beetles (ANOPLORISK: start date 15 December 2010), a team of its researchers visited the USA to exchange information on research progress and see USDA approaches for pest management. This visit was kindly facilitated by our EUPHRESCO Observer (Gordon Gourd, USDA).

Sub-WP 2.3. Evaluate and refine network model and its modus operandi

- The first Milestone (MS 11) is not due until Month 14 (31 March 2012) and is the "First evaluation of *modus operandi*". The *modus operandi* for the future self-sustainable network was presented at the KO meeting in March 2011 and hard copies were distributed with a goal of all partners and especially new partners to familiarise themselves with it.
- Work on the *modus operandi* is therefore ongoing and progress towards the first evaluation at Month 15 is being made.

WP 3: Deepening through transnational research projects

Aim:

This workpackage aims to deepen the European plant health research network cooperation by delivering new transnational research activities, especially coordinated or jointly-funded research projects. These will further support the development and implementation of plant health policy and improve the phytosanitary science base in Europe. Such joint research activities will build additional confidence and experience in joint transnational research commissioning and demonstrate the added value and benefits that result.

The main WP objectives are:

- To identify, prioritise and select transnational research topics suitable for cooperation and collaboration, especially jointly-funded projects, including consultation with current key stakeholders and advisors.
- To initiate transnational research collaborations to support EU plant health policy, operations and science capability.

Summary of WP3 progress for milestones/deliverables since the project's start:

WP3 Milestones		Target	MS Status
MS15	Funding consortia for first round of topics	Month 7	Completed

WP3 Deliverables		Target	DL Status
-	None falling in the period	-	-

Key to milestone progress/status:

 Not started (and/or impact from delay expected)

Sub-WP 3.1. Identify, prioritise and select topics and mechanisms for transnational research activities

- An activity chart along with basic guidelines for the first round of topics (2011) were produced and distributed around the network participants to inform them about the up-coming activities and the proposed scheduled.
- Partners and observers were asked to suggest topics for the first annual round via an online spreadsheet and at the kick-off meeting. Topics were then collected and partners/observers were asked to join the suggested topics as funders thus enabling the interest in each topic to be gauged. Again, the information was collected and a 'Longlist' of potential topics was produced, directly followed by an eligibility check to exclude topics with too few interest or overlaps with existing EUPHRESKO projects. EPPO were also provided with the long list for comment, especially with respect to prioritization.
- For the pre-selection of topics in the 'Longlist after eligibility check', the assignment of a topic coordinator (TC) per topic was used as single criterion. It

was assumed that there might be not enough interest in a topic if there was not a topic coordinator assigned. Furthermore, this criterion was used as the function of the topic coordinator is crucial for the subsequent steps and as this would also be a useful criterion in an automatic topic selection process.

- After the pre-selection process the 'topic list with TCs' was distributed, providing the remaining potential topics for the first call round. Note that all excluded topics were collected into a so called 'parking lists' in order to have them available in the phase of initial suggestions of topics of the second call/round of topics (2012).
- Additionally to the list being distributed, topic coordinators were asked to produce 'short topic descriptions' for all remaining topics, which will be the basis for the subsequent ranking of the topics by the partners. These topic descriptions were produced by the end of July.
- Furthermore, information concerning the potential participation of the partners and observers as funders in the first call round was gathered to be able to provide an overview of the potential funders and funds for this first round of topics/projects.

Sub-WP 3.2 Implement joint research activities

- This Sub-WP will start after topics for the first round have been chosen. Final decisions of topics and funding commitments will be made September/October 2011 and then more detailed topic descriptions and call documents will be developed. Non-competitive projects (direct commissioning) will be initiated around November 2011. Competitive calls will be launched January/February 2012, with projects from successful proposals anticipated to start summer/autumn 2012.
- It should be noted that between the end of EUPHRESCO-1 and the start of EUPHRESCO-2 several new transnational projects have been initiated.
 - ANOPLORISK: "Detection and Risk Management for *Anoplophora* Longhorn Beetles" (€665,000 in total over 2 years; 9 funders from Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, UK; start date 15th December 2011; links established to EU Q-DETECT Project on "detection tools for plant health inspection services" and with USDA)
 - FRUITPHYTOINTERLAB: "Inter-laboratory comparison and validation of detection methods for phytoplasmas of phytosanitary concern in European orchards" (22 research partners) which complements the concurrent COST Action "Integrated Management of Phytoplasma Epidemics in Different Crop Systems FA0807".
 - *Meloidogyne* detection and risk management (16 research partners)
 - *Gibberella circinata* diagnostics (seed testing) (13 research partners)
 - *Dickeya* risk management strategies (in potatoes and bulbs)

WP4: Deepening through improved processes and tools for transnational cooperation

Aim:

The overall aim of WP4 is to develop and enhance approaches for a ‘market place’ for funders that better facilitates and strengthens transnational cooperation in phytosanitary research. The platform will enable information exchanged between funders and/or scientists. It will facilitate faster identification of common priorities, faster coordination of joint expertise and better exploitation of both reference material and specialised facilities. Outputs of this workpackage will feed directly back into WP3 and support and facilitate ongoing transnational activities.

The main WP objectives are:

- To develop improved technical possibilities (platforms/processes) for operating and enhancing the virtual phytosanitary ‘market place’ where common research needs of funders are identified and prioritised. This will include improving, adapting and developing the EUPHRESCO website as a key tool for the market place.
- To facilitate easy exchange and rapid access to information and knowledge between National Plant Protection Organisations, the research establishment, EU bodies, e.g. SANCO, EFSA, and other relevant international institutions, e.g. EPPO.
- To create more opportunities and to explore new and creative ways of delivering transnational funded research that addresses plant health policy, operations and science questions. One particular motivation to develop such enhanced possibilities is the need to react quickly to problems (creation of an emergency track for initiating plant health research, both with regard to the procedure and funds).
- To enhance the potential for transnational research commissioning by identifying specific national barriers to funding collaborations and by exploring strategies to overcome these barriers.
- To explore and enhance linkages to other key stakeholders (both at national and transnational levels) for improved agenda setting and research collaboration, and enhance linkages to plant health activities and coordination mechanisms.

Summary of WP4 progress for milestones/deliverables since the project’s start:

WP4 Milestones		Target	MS Status
-	None falling within the period	-	-

WP4 Deliverables		Target	DL Status
-	None falling within the period	-	-

Key to milestone progress/status:

- Completed
- In progress (no significant impact from delay expected)
- Not started (and/or impact from delay expected)

Sub-WP 4.1. Strengthening platforms and processes for the phytosanitary market place and for information exchange

A workshop, uniting IT-experts and EUPHRESKO representatives was to take place before the summer but had to be postponed until September. The expected outcome will be a shortlist of requirements for the website that are feasible and affordable. In the meantime WP3 has improved on the tools for topic selection and identification of potential co-funders of projects. This information is a valuable input into sub-WP4.1.

Sub-WP 4.2. Creating more opportunities for trans-national funding collaboration

A re-orientation is taking place on the exact scale and scope of the deliverables in this WP. Since the project plan of work was elaborated, other stakeholders have not sat idle. Notably the activities of EFSA need be taken into account.

Sub-WP 4.3. Improve the use of research infrastructure (including specialist knowledge), within Plant Health and with adjacent research areas

No results due within this reporting period.

Sub-WP 4.4. Improve engagement and sense of urgency and responsibility with all stakeholders

No results due within this reporting period.

Additional points:

- An operational guide for WP4 has been produced, detailing the composition of the task groups responsible for the delivery of end products. The guide includes a more concise description of scale and quality of the deliverables.
- WP4 is being co-led by NL-ELI (Eric Regouin) and FR-DGAL (David Caffier). David Caffier has now changed jobs and is unable to provide this input into leading and delivering WP4. The EUPHRESKO Coordinator has written to FR-DGAL and to the French Chief Officer of Plant Health. Informal contacts were made with the French representative in the SCAR. We believe DGAL are working to resolve the issue, but eight months into the project we have not had concrete information on this.
- Unfortunately the Flemish contribution from ILVO became less certain too, jeopardizing some of the task groups coordinated by them. However, this issue has now been resolved as a Belgium colleague from the federal Ministry has expressed willingness and availability to team with the ILVO representative.
- In the meantime, we anticipate that some WP4 activities may be delayed, because of these developments. Any proposed changes to the WP4 workplan will be put to the EC desk officer for consideration and approval.

WP5: Enlarging the Network Cooperation

Aim:

WP5 will aim to increase and encourage the involvement of additional organisations with an interest in transnational research collaborations (e.g. new partners, observers and others). It will broaden the potential cooperation of the network, especially regionally within Europe, more internationally (third countries) and in some previously under-represented sectors (e.g. forestry plant health). Expanding EUPHRSCO's links more internationally will provide research opportunities that will help support the Community Plant Health Regime. In particular, wider international cooperation would enable research on quarantine pests to be done in their countries of origin. International cooperation may be both at the programme level (between national funders) or at the project level (inclusion of more research providers from non-European countries within transnational projects).

The main WP objectives are:

- To attract and integrate more EU member states, associated countries and third countries, e.g. selected International Cooperation Partners Countries (ICPC's) into the EUPHRESO network.
- To explore opportunities and, if relevant, implement regionally-based transnational plant health research (i.e. on specific regionally-based crops or pest issues) and sector-based (plant production sectors, e.g. forestry plant health) under-represented in EUPHRESO-1.
- To explore possibilities and implement, as appropriate, collaborations with third countries, including some ICPC's and developed countries, with similar plant health problems as EU to EUPHRESO-2.
- To explore possibilities and, if possible, implement collaborations with certain third countries (e.g. ICPC's) which are currently sources of plant quarantine pests of concern to the EU.

Summary of WP5 progress for milestones/deliverables since the project's start:

WP5 Milestones		Target	MS Status
MS37	Kick-off meeting for new partners/observers	Month 3	Complete

WP5 Deliverables		Target	DL Status
D5.1	Kick-off meeting for new partners/observers	Month 3	Complete

Key to milestone progress/status:

- Not started (and/or impact from delay expected)

Sub-WP 5.1. Integrating new European Partners, engaging with European Observers and outreach to other European and Mediterranean countries

- A specific workshop to welcome and integrate the new partners and observers to the EUPHRESKO 2 project was held alongside the first KO meeting in Copenhagen on 27th March 2011. The meeting provided a great opportunity for new partners and observers to learn about EUPHRESKO; they heard the success of EUPHRESKO-1, the benefits of being part of EUPHRESKO and the aims and aspirations of EUPHRESKO-2. The workshop had time allocated for each new partner to introduce themselves, to speak about their institutes and the national plant health programmes as well as to share their expectations of the benefits of being part of EUPHRESKO.
- New partners have chosen mentors from the 'old' partners.
- The PMG agreed that the timetable for mapping national programmes in WP2 should be aligned with that in WP5.

Sub-WP 5.2 Exploring regionalisation of specific plant health problems and increased inclusion of plant-producing sectors under-represented in EUPHRESKO-1

- On-going (see also report under WP2)

Sub-WP 5.3. and 5.4: Association of third countries with similar plant health problems as the EU (5.3) and Association of third countries who are the source of quarantine pests of concern to the EU (5.4)

- Steen Lykke Nielsen and several other EUPHRESKO-2 partners active in WP5 participated in the EFSA Scientific Colloquium XIV on Emerging Risks in Plant Health 9th – 10th June 2010 in Parma, Italy. The theme of the Colloquium is very relevant for the WP5 topics: regionalisation and import of plant health problems from third world countries.
- Steen Lykke Nielsen met with Head of Business Development Europe Janny Vos and Business Development Director Philip Abrahams from CABI (who are an Observer in EUPHRESKO-2) at Aarhus University, Research Centre Flakkebjerg the 29th June 2011 to discuss activities in EUPHRESKO-2's WP5 with focus on activities in third world countries to prevent import of plant health problems.

SECTION 3: CONSORTIUM MANAGEMENT (WP1)

WP1: Project coordination and administration

Summary of WP1 progress for milestones/deliverables since the project's start:

WP1 Milestones		Target	MS Status
MS 01	Consortium agreement finalised and signed	Month 3	In progress
MS 02	Governing board and project advisory board	Month 3	In progress
MS 03	EUPHRESCO website updated	Month 3	Completed
MS 04	Kick-off meeting held	Month 3	Completed

WP1 Deliverables		Target	DL Status
D1.1	Governance bodies	Month 3	In Progress
D1.2	6-month report	Month 6	Completed
D1.3	1st e-Newsletter	Month 7	In Progress
D1.5	First Project Management Group Meeting	Month 3	Completed

Key to milestone progress/status:

Not started (and/or impact from delay expected)		
---	---	---

Sub-WP 1.1. Meetings:

- The Kick-off (KO) meeting was held on 24th-25th March 2011 in Copenhagen with Partners and Observers. Additionally, a representative from Poland (NCBRI) attended the meeting; they are a prospective partner and we are continuing to explore the possibility of them joining EUPHRESCO. The Project Management Group (PMG) met on 23rd March. EPPO attended.
- A specific WP5 “new partner and new observer” workshop was held on 27th after the project meeting; with the main aim of welcoming and integrating them into the project. Funds were made available for the observers.
- The second project meeting will be held in February or March 2012 and partners will shortly be asked for their availabilities. The venue for the second meeting has yet to be determined.
- The 3rd PMG meeting will be held at the EPPO headquarters in Paris on 28th September 2011.

Sub-WP 1.2. Reports

- The 6-month report for the Commission was produced.
- A report to the COPHs was produced for their meeting 7-8 June 2011 meeting.

Sub-WP 1.3. Communication

- The project website has been re-launched after the website. Project details have been updated from EUPHRESKO-1 to EUPHRESKO-2.
- The first 6-monthly electronic newsletter is due in Month 7 (31st July) and has been drafted. The website front page invites on-line registration for newsletters. We aim to publicise the newsletter, the launch of EUPHRESKO-2 and the outputs from EUPHRESKO-1 via The European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation (EPPO) website in summer 2011.
- EUPHRESKO posters displaying the aims of EUPHRESKO-2, the successes of EUPHRESKO-1 and some key research project outcomes are available from Fera. They can be loaned for meetings and conferences. The posters have just returned from the Dutch Phytopathological Society annual meeting in Amsterdam.
- The Coordinator attended the 1st EFSA Scientific Network for Risk Assessment in Plant Health in October 2010 (before EUPHRESKO-2 started) as a Hearing Expert representing EUPHRESKO (attendance paid for by EFSA). Continuing opportunities for interaction between EFSA and EUPHRESKO-2 were explored.

Sub-WP 1.4. Project Administration

- The contracts have been signed by all partners and by the Commission. Fera (Coordinator) is waiting for hard copies from the Commission.
- The first advance payment was received from the Commission and is currently been distributed to all project partners in accordance with the conditions of the EU Contract. Fera hopes to have all payments made by the 31st July 2011.
- The virtual Governing Board (GB) membership list has been confirmed and work has started on establishing the 3-5 GB representatives for the Project Advisory Board (PAB). This PAB will be composed of representatives from EUPHRESKO-1's previous Expert Advisory Group (EPPO, EFSA and DG SANCO) as well as some GB members. Ideally, GB representatives on the PAB should meet some of the following criteria (as discussed at the first Project Management Group meeting):
 - Links to COPHS/SCAR/EPPO
 - Experience with other ERA-Nets
 - Links to JPI's
 - Balance between N,S,E,W of Europe
 - Pro-activity and availability now and for the long-term network.

GB members will be asked to nominate themselves or other GB members as candidates for the PAB. A letter has been drafted from the Chair of the GB (Martin Ward, Fera), which will be sent to GB members very shortly.

- The Project Management Group (PMG) met on 25th February and 23rd March 2011, to progress the first few project tasks and to discuss the kick-off (KO)

meeting and the first WP5 workshop to make these two events as interesting and as useful as possible for everybody involved. Technical, management, communication and governance issues were also discussed.

- A consortium agreement (CA) is currently being drafted and once ready will be sent round all partners for comments before being finalised. It is based on the previous CA for EUPHRESCO-1
- A forward job plan (FJP) has been produced for each workpackage as a management tool for WP leaders. Updates are notified and will be made accessible via the 'member's pages' of the project website. As a minimum, the FJP is updated before/after the 6-monthly PMG meetings.
- The Coordinator has been internally logging various Partner changes (e.g. organisational names) and will approach the Commission shortly about such changes.
- The Coordinator and Partners made entries onto NetWatch.